

STOCHASTIC SIMULATION OF COMPOSITES CURE

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Keywords: *Cure, Stochastic Simulation, Monte Carlo, Probabilistic Collocation Method*

1 Introduction

Fabrication of fibrous thermosetting composites is a very complex activity, involving different processes such as forming, consolidation/impregnation and curing. Each of the steps of the manufacturing process incorporates several sources of uncertainty which introduce variability to the subsequent steps creating strong interdependencies between the material properties and process parameters of the final part. The main sources of uncertainty are associated with (i) fibre misalignment which can be generated during production, storage or handling of pre-pregs, preforms, and dry textiles, (ii) matrix material uncertainties caused by variations in resin composition/formulation and different shelf life history conditions, and (iii) environmental/boundary conditions uncertainties related to process parameter variations [1-2]. All these can introduce significant variability to the curing step causing serious defects, such as over-cure, under-cure, cure-induced voids, distortion and thermal degradation [2-3]. Different resin handling and storage conditions can result in cure kinetics uncertainty [4-6]. Process parameter uncertainties including cure temperature and heat convection coefficient variations can introduce variability to the heat transfer phenomena taking place during the curing step [7-8]. Fibre misalignment and fibre volume fraction variations can introduce significant scatter to the mechanical, thermal, and thermo-mechanical properties of the constituent materials affecting the curing process [7,9]. Fibre volume fraction variations can also introduce variability to the level of residual stresses [10-11].

Deterministic process simulation models do not incorporate these stochastic effects and as a consequence are not able to capture the real

phenomena leading in many cases to poor results. Therefore, stochastic simulation is becoming increasingly important due to the interest in predicting variability in composites manufacturing. Stochastic simulation results have shown that cure kinetics and cure temperature variations can introduce significant variability in cure time, with the cure temperature being the dominant variable [2]. In addition, it has been indicated that faster reacting resin systems can show higher cure time variability than systems with higher activation energy [2]. However, these results were based on theoretical values of input uncertainty rather than experimental data. As a result, a fundamental gap exists on the characterization of input parameters uncertainty in composites cure.

The present study focuses on the characterization of cure kinetics uncertainty due to different resin handling/storage conditions and its effect on the cure behavior. A series of experiments was carried out using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) to characterize cure kinetics uncertainty of a commercial epoxy resin used in aerospace applications. The resulting stochastic simulation problem is addressed by coupling a cure kinetics model with traditional Monte Carlo Scheme (MCS) and the Probabilistic Collocation Method (PCM). The capabilities of the collocation method have been demonstrated in the context of composite manufacturing in the case of simulation of Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) filling stage [16]. The two stochastic simulation approaches are implemented considering the cure process of the epoxy system of this work. The two schemes are compared in terms of accuracy and computational time.

2 Methodology

2.1 Deterministic cure kinetics model

The cure kinetics model used in this study is appropriate for a commercial epoxy resin used in aerospace applications [12].

The cure reaction rate is defined as:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = k_1(1-a)^{n_1} + k_2(1-a)^{n_2} a^m \quad (1)$$

where a is the current degree of cure, k_1 , k_2 the reaction rate constants, and m , n_1 , n_2 the reaction orders. The reaction rate constants are calculated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{k_i} = \frac{1}{k_{i,c}} + \frac{1}{k_d} \quad i=1,2 \quad (2)$$

where $k_{i,c}$ are chemical rate constants, and k_d is a diffusion rate constant, defined as:

$$k_d = A_D \exp\left(\frac{-E_D}{RT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-b}{f}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$k_{i,c} = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{RT}\right) \quad i=1,2 \quad (4)$$

where T is the current cure temperature, E_i activation energies, A_i pre-exponential factors, A_D and E_D the pre-exponential factor and activation energy of the diffusion process, respectively, R the universal gas constant, b a constant, and f the equilibrium free volume given by:

$$f = 0.00048(T - T_g) + 0.025 \quad (5)$$

where T_g is the instantaneous glass transition temperature defined as:

$$T_g = T_{g^o} + \frac{(T_{g^\infty} - T_{g^o})\lambda a}{1 - (1 - \lambda)a} \quad (6)$$

Here T_{g^o} and T_{g^∞} denote the glass transition temperatures for the uncured and fully cured material, respectively, while λ is a fitting constant [13].

The cure process of the epoxy resin was simulated by integrating numerically, to compute the instantaneous cure reaction rate and the degree of cure evolution. Explicit numerical integration was used. Fig. 1 illustrates the applied cure profile.

2.2 Analysis of input parameters uncertainty

2.2.1 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was utilized to characterize cure kinetics variation. All tests were equilibrated at 80 °C and then a heating rate of 1°C/min was applied up to 240 °C. Samples from four different batches as well as different samples from every batch were tested. All samples were within their lifetime.

2.2.2 Quantification of cure kinetics uncertainty

As shown in Fig. 2, the range of cure kinetics variability was quantified by fitting the cure kinetics simulation model to the experimental data. In particular, a Genetic Algorithm described in detail in [14] was used to determine a new set of cure kinetics parameters by fitting the cure kinetics simulation model described in section 2.1 to the experimental data. Since the initial degree of cure cannot be computed using the cure kinetics model, its scatter was quantified by fitting the kinetics parameters resulted from the previous step to each of the experimental curves. The latter was performed using the Microsoft Excel solver. This procedure was iterated several times until a satisfactory fit was achieved. A factorial design was carried out to determine the cure kinetics influential factors. The influential factors were then fitted to each experimental curve to determine the range of uncertainty for each parameter. Having determined the uncertain parameters and the range of their uncertainty, a sensitivity analysis was performed using the cure kinetics model to determine which of the uncertain parameters should be considered as stochastic during the stochastic cure simulation. During the sensitivity analysis all variables were

varied over $\pm 2\sigma$, where σ is the standard deviation of each variable.

2.3 Stochastic cure simulation

2.3.1 Monte Carlo Scheme

A crude Monte Carlo scheme was developed and coupled with the cure kinetics model to investigate the effect of inputs variability on the process output parameters. Random samples are generated for each stochastic variable. The number of samples is dictated by convergence criteria. Given that the mean value of a parameter converges faster than its standard deviation, the number of samples is determined by the convergence of the standard deviation. Due to random sampling, a quite large number of the deterministic model runs are required to ensure convergence and accuracy, implying high computational cost.

2.3.2 Probabilistic Collocation Method

In addition to the traditional Monte Carlo Scheme, a stochastic simulation model based on the Probabilistic Collocation Method was developed and coupled with the cure kinetics model presented in section 2.1.

The main concept of this method is to construct a response surface for every output parameter, as a function of uncertain parameters in the form of orthogonal polynomials, called the polynomial chaos. Details concerning the construction of the polynomial chaos can be found in [17]. Having constructed a response surface for each output parameter, a statistical analysis is carried out to quantify output parameters uncertainty.

Following this strategy, the stochastic problem is significantly reduced in calculating the unknown polynomial chaos coefficients, which are computed using the probabilistic collocation approach [18]. The collocation points are the roots of the next higher order orthogonal polynomial than the order of the response surface and are chosen so that the residuals between each response surface and corresponding model outputs is zero, implying that the collocation points are selected from regions of high probability. Consequently, a system of linear equations is obtained to calculate the polynomial

chaos coefficients for every output parameter [18]. This concept is depicted in Fig. 3. The largest discrepancies between the response surface and the actual model occur at regions of low probability, thus only a small error is produced.

In the case of Gaussian variables, the polynomial chaos is defined as a set of Hermite polynomials [18]. The first, second and third order polynomials are:

$$H_1(y) = y \quad (7)$$

$$H_2(y) = y^2 - 1 \quad (8)$$

$$H_3(y) = y^3 - 3y \quad (9)$$

where y is the standard random normal variable. For example, combinations of the roots of the third order Hermite polynomial ($\pm 1.732, 0$) comprise the set of collocation points for a second order response surface.

2.3.3 Stochastic simulation

The covariance matrix C and the vector of the mean values μ include all the information regarding the statistical properties of the stochastic variables and their cross-correlation.

The Cholesky decomposition was implemented in both stochastic simulation schemes to generate realizations of the stochastic variables. By definition, the covariance matrix C is symmetric and positive definite and can be expressed as:

$$C = LL^T \quad (10)$$

where L is a lower triangular matrix and is the Cholesky root. The product of the Cholesky root with the vector Y of independent identically distributed normal variables is a vector V that encompasses the statistical properties of the stochastic variables, and is defined as follows:

$$V = LY \quad (11)$$

The methodology described by Eqs. (10) and (11) is implemented in two steps. First, the Cholesky root is

evaluated as defined in Eq. (10). This step has relatively high computational cost; however, it needs to be executed only once. Realisations of the random vector Y are then generated and transformed to realisations of the vector V using Eq. (11). This step is computationally cheap and is executed several times equal to the number of required realisations of the stochastic variables.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Statistical properties of input parameters

Fig. 4. depicts experimental results obtained by a series of dynamic DSC scans, along with cure simulation results (before fitting) using the cure kinetics model for the epoxy system of this work. The results show consistency; however, the discrepancies are not negligible, implying variability in cure kinetics. A shift between the experimental curves is present, whilst the magnitude of the maximum cure reaction rate shows significant discrepancies. In addition, discrepancies occur at temperatures above 220 °C, where diffusion phenomena are dominant.

Based on the methodology described in section 2.2.2 the parameters showing variability and their statistical properties, including the mean value, μ , the standard deviation, σ , and the coefficient of variation (σ/μ), are presented in Table 1. The initial degree of cure exhibits the highest level of uncertainty, with the reaction order showing more moderate values and the activation energies to follow.

Sensitivity analysis results suggested that the initial degree of cure can influence the temperature the reaction is taking place, thus can introduce a shift to the cure reaction rate - temperature curve, while the reaction order, n_2 and the activation energy, E_2 affect the magnitude of the maximum cure reaction rate. Moreover, the activation energy, E_1 , mainly affects the cure behavior at temperatures above 220 °C.

As a result, the activation energy, E_1 , was considered deterministic in this study, since it has negligible effects on the cure process for the given cure profile (see Fig. 4). Therefore, the activation energy E_2 , the initial degree of cure a_0 , and the reaction order n_2 , were treated as stochastic variables during the stochastic cure simulation. Due to the limited number of experimental data and the fact that the

purpose of this study is to capture the most generic case, all stochastic variables were assumed to follow a normal distribution. Moreover, according to the data presented in Table 1, none of the parameters can reach a negative value even in the case of high scatter.

The correlation matrix of the stochastic variables is presented in Table 2. Examination of the correlation matrix indicates that the initial degree of cure, a_0 , and the reaction order, n_2 , are strongly correlated, while no strong correlation exists between the other parameters. There is no clear evidence regarding this behavior. Besides, investigation of this behavior is beyond the scope of this work.

3.2 Stochastic cure simulation results

The two stochastic simulation approaches described in the previous sections were implemented to investigate the effect of cure kinetics uncertainty on the cure behaviour of neat epoxy resin.

In the Collocation method implementation, a second order response surface was constructed to represent the cure reaction rate. A modified regression-based collocation approach was implemented to improve accuracy. The number of collocation points used was larger than the number of the unknown polynomial chaos coefficients, implying that the effect of each collocation point is reduced. In particular, the number of the unknown coefficients for a three dimensional second order polynomial chaos is 10 [17], however, 21 collocation points were used in this study, implying that only 21 deterministic model runs are required. In addition, a crude Monte Carlo simulation was performed to carry out the statistical analysis using the constructed response surface.

The cure reaction rate as a function of time is illustrated in Fig. 5. As it can be observed, the maximum cure reaction rate as well as the region before the second ramp exhibit significant variability. More specifically, the maximum cure reaction rate presents 7.5 % coefficient of variation. This can introduce variability to the temperature overshoot as well as influence the cure time for different cure cycles. No considerable variability is presented in the remainder regions. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 depict the evolution of statistics of the cure reaction rate as a function time, for the two stochastic simulation schemes. The results suggest that a very

good agreement is achieved between the Monte Carlo scheme and the Collocation method, especially for the mean value. The convergence of the statistics of the mean and the standard deviation of the maximum cure reaction rate is presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. A quite satisfactory convergence is achieved after 2×10^3 Monte Carlo realizations, with the discrepancies between the two methods being negligible. The histogram of the maximum cure reaction rate presented in Fig. 10 also confirms the good agreement between the two stochastic simulation approaches. Examination of the probability distribution of the maximum cure reaction rate shown in Fig. 11 indicates that the maximum cure reaction rate can be described by a Weibull distribution.

The results presented here suggest that cure kinetics variability due to different resin handling/storage conditions can significantly affect the curing process with potential implications in the temperature overshoot and the cure time. Moreover, the Probabilistic Collocation Method has clearly demonstrated its capabilities in this context.

4 Concluding Remarks

The methodologies developed in this work aim at quantifying the propagation of variability to the cure process outcome. The results of experiments showed that the cure behavior of high specification thermosets could involve uncertainty, which in turn can introduce significant variability to the cure behavior. The stochastic simulation results suggest that the maximum cure reaction rate can present variability in the order of 7.5 %, with potential implications in the temperature overshoot and cure time.

Both MCS and PCM have the capability of capturing variability propagation, with the MCS presenting a computationally expensive and rich solution and the PCM offering an efficient approximation (e.g. for the given case, the computational cost of the PCM is 1.5 % of that of the MCS), with comparable accuracy.

The modeling approaches presented in this work can be coupled with process simulation to investigate the effect of cure kinetics variability on heat transfer effects taking place during the cure.

Acknowledgement

Financial support by the EPSRC Centre for Innovative Manufacturing in Composites (EP/I033513/1) is gratefully acknowledged.

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variable	a_o	E_1	E_2	n_2
μ	0.038	78126	55970	1.9
σ	0.0043	929.4	182.8574	0.068127
σ/μ (%)	11.1	1.2	0.33	3.6

Table 1. Statistical properties of uncertain parameters

variable	a_o	E_2	n_2
a_o	1	-0.005	-0.4
E_2	-0.005	1	0.14
n_2	-0.4	0.14	1

Table 2. Correlation matrix of stochastic variables

Fig. 1. Cure profile.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of methodology for quantification of cure kinetics uncertainty.

Fig. 3. Collocation points selection at high probability region.

Fig. 4. Evolution of reaction rate with temperature during dynamic cure.

Fig. 5. Cure reaction rate vs time-Monte Carlo.

Fig. 8. Convergence of statistics of mean of maximum cure reaction rate vs time.

Fig. 6. Evolution of mean of cure reaction rate vs time.

Fig. 9. Convergence of statistics of standard deviation of maximum cure reaction rate vs time.

Fig. 7. Evolution of standard deviation of cure reaction rate vs time.

Fig. 10. Histogram of maximum cure reaction rate [1/sec].

Fig. 11. Probability distribution of maximum cure reaction rate.